

Application of Reimer and Tiemann Reaction to *m*-Halogeno-Phenols

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***m*-Halogeno-phenols were subjected to Reimer and Tiemann reaction. From *m*-chloro and *m*-bromo-phenol, one chloro and one bromo-salicylaldehyde was obtained. *m*-Iodo-phenol, however, gave two isomeric iodo-salicylaldehydes. The chloro and bromo-salicylaldehydes were found to be different from those reported earlier by the same reaction. Of the two isomeric iodo-salicylaldehydes, one was found to be 4-iodo-salicylaldehyde isolated earlier. The second isomer was found to be a new one. On the basis of cyclisations of these salicylaldehydes to coumarin derivatives, their reduction to halogeno-*o*-cresols and the study of NMR spectra correct structures were assigned to halogeno-salicylaldehydes obtained in this reaction.**

Hodgson and Jakinson^{1,2} studied the application of Reimer and Tiemann reaction to *m*-halogeno-phenols and reported the isolation of 4-halogeno-salicylaldehydes I and 2-halogeno-4-hydroxy benzaldehydes III as the reaction products. When the work of Hodgson and Jakinson was repeated, it was observed that *m*-chloro and *m*-bromo-phenol gave a chloro and a bromo-salicylaldehyde each. From *m*-iodo-phenol, however, it was possible to isolate two isomeric iodo-salicylaldehydes. 2-Halogeno-4-hydroxy-benzaldehydes reported earlier were also obtained in all the three cases.

The melting points of chloro and bromo-salicylaldehydes were found to be slightly higher than those reported by Hodgson and Jakinson. The melting point of one of the two isomeric iodo-salicylaldehydes was found to be identical with 4-iodo-salicylaldehyde reported by the same authors. The iodo-salicylaldehyde with melting point 62° was found to have not been reported in literature.

On theoretical grounds, two isomeric halogeno salicylaldehydes are likely to be formed when *m*-halogenophenols are subjected to Reimer and Tiemann reaction (Fig. 1). The salicylaldehydes isolated should, therefore, be either 4-halogeno-salicylaldehyde I or 6-halogeno salicylaldehydes II.

On cyclization with acetic anhydride structures I and II lead to the formation of 7-halogeno-coumarins IV and 5-halogeno coumarins V respectively.

In order to check the structures, halogeno-salicylaldehydes were cyclised to coumarins using acetic anhydride and the cyclised products were compared with the known 7-chloro³ and 7-bromo⁴ coumarins. 7-Iodo-coumarin required for comparison was obtained by condensing *m*-iodo-phenol with malic acid. The coumarins obtained by cyclization of chloro, bromo and iodo-salicylaldehyde (m.p. 52°) were found to be different from the corresponding 7-halogeno coumarins. The coumarin obtained from the iodo-salicylaldehyde (m.p. 84°) was however found to be identical with 7-iodo-coumarin. The formation of

different coumarin derivatives than 7-halogeno-coumarins can only be explained if chloro, bromo and iodo-salicylaldehyde (m.p. 62°) are represented as 6-halogenosalicylaldehydes II. The iodo-salicylaldehyde (m.p. 84°) can, however, be represented as 4-iodo-salicylaldehyde I as it gave 7-iodo-coumarin IV on cyclization.

To have an additional evidence in support of the structure II for the chloro, bromo and iodo-salicylaldehyde (m.p. 62°), the reduction of these compounds by Wolf-Kishner method was studied. The chloro and bromo-salicylaldehydes were reduced to known 3-chloro⁵ and 3-bromo-*o*-cresols⁶ VII respectively. The iodo-salicylaldehyde (m.p. 62°), however, resisted the reduction. The formation of 3-halogeno-*o*-cresols can be explained only if the aldehydes are 6-halogeno-salicylaldehydes. 4-Halogeno-salicylaldehydes I would have given 5-halogeno-*o*-cresols VI.

NMR Spectra: 6-halogeno-salicylaldehydes are tri-substituted benzene derivatives. The relative positions of CH = O, -OH and halogens are 1, 2 and 6 respectively. The -CH = O protons of the three salicylaldehyde derivatives, appear near 10 PPM (Table 2). Due to intramolecular hydrogen bonding CH = O protons come in the vicinity of electronegative halogens (Fig. 2). The electronegativity of halogens decrease from chlorine to iodine and as a result the shielding of CH = O proton is expected to be in the following order in the three halogeno salicylaldehydes.

Had the compounds been 4-halogeno-salicylaldehydes, there would not have been deshielding due to halogeno groups. As a result of this there would not be a gradual change in the δ -values of CH = O protons. δ -values of CH = O protons are in good agreements with the electronegativities of halogens. The -OH protons in three halogenosalicylaldehydes appear around 12 ppm and are indicative of a very strong intramolecular hydrogen bonding.

TABLE 1

Physical constants of halogeno salicylaldehydes, halogeno coumarins and halogeno-o-cresols

Name of the compound	M.P. °C	Analysis. Halogens %		Yield %
		Reqd.	Found	
6-chloro-salicylaldehyde	55	22.12	22.20	3
6-bromo-salicylaldehyde	52.5	39.80	39.72	2
6-iodo-salicylaldehyde	62	51.00	51.20	1
5-chloro-coumarin	92	19.40	19.32	49
5-bromo-coumarin	97	35.50	35.90	40
5-iodo-coumarin	108	46.70	46.52	45
7-iodo-coumarin	172	46.70	46.95	45
3-chloro- <i>o</i> -cresol	86	—	—	5
3-bromo- <i>o</i> -cresol	96.5	—	—	5

Phenyl protons (5) ortho to halogen again show a regular shift in the three halogeno salicylaldehydes which is in good agreement with the electronegativity of halogens (Table 2). NMR spectra indicate that the largest contribution to the structure of halogeno salicylaldehydes is probably due to the following canonical structure.

TABLE 2

NMR data of 6-halogeno-salicylaldehydes

Name of the compound	Phenyl protons				
	δ - -CH = 0	δ - -OH	δ -H ₃	δ -H ₄	δ -H ₅
6-Chloro-salicylaldehydes	10.4	11.8	6.8	7.4	6.9
6-Bromo-salicylaldehydes	10.3	11.9	6.9	7.3	7.25
6-Iodo-salicylaldehydes	10.05	12.0	6.8	7.15	7.45

X = Cl, Br, I

The chemical evidences and the NMR spectra, therefore, prove beyond doubt that chloro, bromo and iodo-salicylaldehydes under consideration are 6-halogeno-salicylaldehydes.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

(Physical constants and analysis is given in Table 1).

Halogeno-salicylaldehydes : The solution of *m*-halogenophenol (0.5 mole) in aqueous sodium hydroxide (3 ml NaOH in 300 ml water) was subjected to Reimer and Tiemann reaction using chloroform (0.7 mol) and following the usual procedure. Compounds obtained were first purified by bi-sulphite treatment and then by crystallisation from ethanol. In the case of *m*-chloro and *m*-bromo only one compound was obtained. While from *m*-iodophenol two isomeric salicylaldehydes were obtained by fractionation from ethanol water mixture. One compound separated as pale-yellow, short needles and the other as thin lustrous plates.

Halogeno coumarins : To the solution of halogeno-salicylaldehyde (0.01 mol) in acetic anhydride (0.06 mol) freshly fused sodium acetate (0.02 mol) was added and the mixture was heated under reflux on oil bath at 160–70° for 1 hr and then at 170°–80° for 5 hr. The reaction mixture was then cooled and poured over crushed ice. The solid obtained was filtered and treated with dilute sodium hydroxide to remove acidic impurities. The sodium hydroxide insoluble residue was washed with water and crystallised from 20% ethanol. Woolly needles were obtained in all the four cases.

Condensation of m-iodo-phenol with malic acid : A mixture of *m*-iodo-phenol (17 gm), active malic acid (15 gm) and con. sulphuric acid (35 ml) was heated in an oil bath at 130° for 30 min. The temperature of the oil bath was then raised gradually to 160° and was maintained till the evolution of carbon dioxide ceased. The reaction mixture was then cooled to room temperature and then poured over crushed ice. The solid obtained was filtered, and treated with cold dilute sodium hydroxide solution. Most of the solid dissolved leaving a small quantity of insoluble residue. The sodium hydroxide insoluble residue was filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from 60% acetic acid. Short long pinkish needles were obtained.

Halogeno-salicylaldehyde hydrazones : To the solution of halogeno salicylaldehyde (0.01 mol) in ethanol (15 ml) aqueous solution of hydrazine sulphate (0.03 mol in 10 ml water) was added. The reaction mixture was heated on water bath for 30 min to complete the reaction. Yellow crystalline solid obtained was filtered and washed with water. Since these compounds were practically insoluble in water and organic solvents they could not be recrystallised.

Halogeno-o-cresols : Mixture of halogeno-salicylaldehyde hydrazone (0.5 m) and aqueous solution of sodium hydroxide (5 gm in 5 ml of water) was refluxed for 24 hr. The reaction mixture was then cooled and filtered to remove unreacted hydrazone. The clear filtrate was acidified with hydrochloric acid (5 *N*) and the acidified solution was extracted with ether. The solid obtained on evaporation of ether was crystallised from water.

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